

POTENTIAL FOR CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS RECOVERY FROM HUNGARIAN RED MUD

Éva UJACZKI^{1,2}, Yannick S. ZIMMERMANN^{1,3}, Christoph A. GASSER^{1,3},
Mónika MOLNÁR², Viktória FEIGL², Markus LENZ^{1,4}

¹Institute for Ecopreneurship, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, School of Life Sciences, Gründenstrasse 40, 4132 Muttenz, Switzerland

²Department of Applied Biotechnology and Food Science, Faculty of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Műegyetem rkp. 3, 1111 Budapest, Hungary

³Institute for Environmental Research (Biology V), RWTH Aachen University, 52074 Aachen, Germany

⁴Sub-Department of Environmental Technology, Wageningen University, 6700 AA Wageningen, The Netherlands

Corresponding Author: markus.lenz@fhnw.ch

Introduction

The world economy is confronted with an increasing supply risk of critical raw materials (CRMs). These are defined as materials with high supply risk and above average economic importance compared to other raw materials [1]. Rare earth elements (REEs) have received considerable attention in the past years, partly as a result of the dramatic REE price surge when China – producing more than 95% of the annual world supply of REEs – had introduced tight export quota for REEs, because of the domestic demands [2]. Though in 2011 the quotas and the export tariffs were eliminated, prices are still above pre-2011 values [3]. The supply risk can be reduced, if so far untapped sources (primary, secondary) can be exploited in the future. One such untapped secondary source for CRMs is so called red mud. Red muds are the residues generated from alumina production where bauxite is digested in hot sodium hydroxide solution by the Bayer process. Currently, an estimated 2.7 billion tons worldwide is produced every year, and is expected to increase by approximately 120 million tons per annum [4]. Alternative uses for red mud have so far not found an industrial application besides use in cement and ceramic production. Red mud can contain considerable amounts of CRMs and further raw materials with high relative economic importance. Extraction of such metals from red mud can be economically feasible [5]. However, a detailed inventory of economic value in red muds of different origin does not exist so far. This research, therefore, discusses the possibilities to recover economically interesting elements from Hungarian red mud.

Materials and Methods

Here, for the first time exhaustive inventory of valuable elements (CRMs including REEs) in Hungarian red muds was created using both X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) as well as microwave assisted aqua regia digestion with subsequent Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis. Next, a number of conventional extracting agents (H_2SO_4 , HCl , HNO_3) were evaluated for their REE recovery potential. Small molecular weight organic acids (citric acid, oxalic acid) were benchmarked to evaluate the potential of heterotrophic bioleaching as green alternative to chemical leaching [1]. Also, the optimal extraction conditions maximizing the overall economic potential of minor metals (and not mere metal concentrations of a limited number of elements) were determined using a design of experiment approach. Finally, a 2 step downstream purification (precipitation + LLE) of CRM (in particular REEs) from red mud hydrochloric acid leachates was developed. After initial evaluation of LLE efficiencies using four explanatory variables (i.e. LLE organic/aqueous ratio; D2EHPA concentration, stripping organic/aqueous ratio, HCl concentration) the optimal extraction conditions maximizing the economic potential of CRMs were determined using a design of experiment approach. The accuracy of design of experiment predictions was verified by laboratory tests.

Results

Comparing different acids, hydrochloric acid (HCl) yielded the highest REEs efficiency (Table 1) [6].

Table 1 Extraction efficiencies for HCl , H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$ and $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ at a normality = 2; 24h; 60°C and 100 g L^{-1} slurry concentration.

Element	Aqua regia accessible [mg kg^{-1}]	HCl [mg kg^{-1}]	H_2SO_4 [mg kg^{-1}]	HNO_3 [mg kg^{-1}]	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$ [mg kg^{-1}]	$\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ [mg kg^{-1}]
Al	56401	47508	47453	51541	45230	5054
Cr	646	73	61	64	74	204
Fe	214175	6529	4130	2502	6083	4389
Co	60	19	15	15	17	39
Ga	27	12	9	11	8	16
In	1	0	0	0	0	0
Total REEs	1082	475	289	367	372	2

Increasing HCl concentrations from 0.5 to 6 M led to considerably increased extraction efficiencies of REEs. The best results regarding contact time were

achieved at 3 hours. Significant ($p < 0.05$) differences in the extraction efficiencies were observed between 22 °C, 50 °C and 60 °C for REEs. A slight but significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease was detectable at increasing slurry concentration from 10 to 100 g L⁻¹ for REEs. Regarding downstream processing, we could show efficient separation of Fe by pH induced precipitation and removal of Al with the raffinate during subsequent LLE. Ultimately, more than > 40% of the overall REEs (> 62% of the leachable REEs) in red mud could be purified using LLE, whereas Al + Fe were successfully rejected from the concentrate (~5% of the overall Al and 7% of the overall Fe present).

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